

Sleep unconsciousness and breakdown of serial critical intermittency: New vistas on the global workspace

Paolo Allegrini^{a,b,*}, Paolo Paradisi^c, Danilo Menicucci^{a,b}, Marco Laurino^{a,d}, Remo Bedini^{a,b}, Andrea Piarulli^{b,e}, Angelo Gemignani^{a,b,d}

^a Istituto di Fisiologia Clinica (IFC-CNR), Via Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy

^b Centro EXTREME, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, P.zza Martiri della Libertà 7, 56127 Pisa, Italy

^c Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione "A. Faedo" (ISTI-CNR), Via Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy

^d Dipartimento di Patologia Chirurgica, Medica, Molecolare e dell'area critica, Università di Pisa, Via Paradisa 2, 56127 Pisa, Italy

^e PERCeptual Robotics laboratory, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, P.zza Martiri della Libertà 7, 56127 Pisa, Italy

A B S T R A C T

While several mental functions are characterized by parallel computation performed by moduli in the cortex, consciousness is sustained by a serial global integration: a single scene at a time takes place. Studies on complex systems show that macroscopic variables, integrating many components activities, undergo fluctuations with an intermittent serial structure when the system is in a state called "criticality", characterized by avalanches with inverse-power-law (scale-free) distribution densities of sizes and inter-event times. Criticality has been established in human brain dynamics during wakefulness. Here we review how the critical hypothesis is able to explain many recent studies on brain complex dynamics. We focus, in particular, on the global, serial, intermittent behavior that can be assessed via high-density electroencephalograms, studying transitions between metastable states. Established as it is during wakefulness, it remained unsolved whether this global intermittent dynamics correlates with consciousness or with a non-task-driven default mode, also present in non-conscious states, like deep (NREM) sleep. Here we show that in NREM sleep seriality breaks down, and re-establishes during REM sleep (dreams), with unaltered spacial structure, in terms of complex branching of avalanches. We conjecture that this connectivity is exploited in NREM sleep by neural bistability, resetting and "parallelizing" portions of the cortex.

1. Introduction

Defining Consciousness is elusive. Many features of consciousness have been proposed by psychologists and neurophysiologists, varying from vigilance to the presence or expression of cognitive or emotional functions. Along this line, consciousness can be studied in an analytical way, namely via the study of the various outputs correlating with it. Deep, or dreamless, sleep is the only physiolog-

ical state characterized by absence of consciousness. Other conditions of lack of consciousness are typically pathological and range from neural to cardiovascular till to metabolic dysfunctions (e.g., epilepsy, syncopes, coma, severe hypoglycemia).

On the other hand, there is consensus among psychologists that consciousness is fully present during structured oneiric activity (dreaming with presence and gestalt) typically reported after awakenings from REM sleep. Although, according to recent literature (see [1] for a review), mental activity has been reported also in non-REM phases, here for simplicity we rest on the hypothesis that *conscious* dreaming is the typical function of REM sleep. We will come back to this point later, near the end of our paper (specifically in

* Corresponding author at: Istituto di Fisiologia Clinica (IFC-CNR), Via Moruzzi 1, 56124 Pisa, Italy. Tel.: +39 3332250303.

E-mail addresses: allegrip@df.unipi.it, allegrinipaolo@yahoo.it (P. Allegrini).

the caption of Fig. 7), where we will see what kind of activity may be present when the global workspace is fragmented.

Thus, studying the differences in neural correlates of NREM sleep, with respect to wakefulness or dreams, provides a spotlight to investigate consciousness. On the other hand, the very presence of consciousness remains private, thus impossible to be reduced to a list of features [2]. One way around this philosophical difficulty is to adopt a different route to scientific reduction, namely focusing on the “downwards causation” of an emerging complex phenomenon onto measurable features. This means that output features must be considered necessary, but never sufficient to describe consciousness.

In this paper, we first review concepts linking consciousness, seriality, intermittency and criticality. This should help in understanding the emergence and quenching of consciousness during wakefulness and dreaming on one side, and dreamless sleep on the other.

Then we present a holistic measure stemming from electroencefalogram (EEG) recording, showing how intermittency is lost during non-REM (NREM) sleep, where structured oneiric activity (*gestalt*) is thought to be absent. Finally we present a rather simple heuristic view, based on sleep physiology, that may allow to link consciousness and complexity in terms of an *emerging* global workspace.

2. Criticality: theoretical implications

2.1. Entropy issues

Evidence is growing that the conscious self is a holistic auto-organization phenomenon, to be tackled using the framework of complexity theories, like, for instance, renormalization group relations [3] that effectively describe critical phenomena, characterized by diverging correlations in space (or structure) and time due to rescaling symmetries (autosimilarity). These introduce “redundancies”, thermodynamically (i.e., for macroscopic volumes) making the entropy per volume tend to zero. This actually does not imply a vanishing entropy for the whole system, thermodynamically occurring only at absolute-zero temperature. This means that entropy ceases, at criticality, to be an extensive quantity for the system. This is easily understandable by envisaging entropy in the Gibbs sense ($S = \log W$, where W is the number of possible microstates): structural infinite correlations prevents different subsystems of a critical system to become statistically independent, so that $W \neq \prod W_i$, thus $S \neq \sum S_i$, where i is a subsystem label.

An emphasis on information is gaining momentum to objectively define the eluding concept of consciousness. According to Tononi’s *integrated information theory* [4], consciousness is associated with a critical interplay between integration and segregation in functional neural networks, and, neglecting the epistemic problems earlier exposed, a measure of consciousness was proposed, namely the difference Φ between the sum of the local Kolmogorov entropies and the global one. As a result, conscious (high- Φ) neural circuits have to be critically balanced between integration and independence [5]. In

this way, “consciousness” is low (or absent) both when the system is perfectly integrated (synchronicity) or completely segregated (no global integration).

2.2. Scale-free networks

The dynamical rules implemented in [4], however, are such that the only property that can be responsible of a change in global behavior is a change in topology [6]. In a toy model of brain [7] one can start pruning an all-to-all network till to recover a first-neighbor one, passing from synchronization to local segregation: Complex dynamical behavior is seen in between, when the network is complex.

We remark that similar models, for virtually every kind of non-disjoint network, can yield complex behavior. Complexity is established by varying the so called *control parameter*, e.g. the neuron-neuron coupling or, alternatively, the noise. Remarkably, at the critical point the functional connectivity develops long-range correlations, resulting in an effective “functional” complex scale-free network [8]. Here functional connectivity is defined as the network of above-threshold cross-correlations. Complexity Φ thus reaches its maximum at the critical point of any neural-network model (e.g., of Kuramoto oscillators, or others [9,10]), when a fluctuating functional network emerges with scale-free properties. The fixed or slowly-changing “anatomical” topology has the only role of shifting the critical point in the control-parameter space [11]. Interestingly, in [11] it has been hypothesized that the critical point is a more fundamental postulate than Hebbian learning, that in fact provides a convenient rule to attain criticality by minimizing “resources” in terms of coupling (number and amount of neurotransmitters) or wiring (number of synapses). In other words, Hebbian plasticity, when expressed at the critical point, favors the emergence and consolidations of a scale-free-network topology.

2.3. Avalanches

Another signature of criticality is the presence of avalanches, where the term avalanche denotes the rapid domino-like transmission of excitation from one node to the other, with an inverse-power law distribution of the number of nodes involved, called avalanche size. This topological scale-free feature was indeed predicted by some authors [12,13] as a critical-point, separating a quenched and an explosively expanding behavior in the transmission of excitation through layers of neurons. Finally, we remark that the critical branching defines another kind of complex networks and is subtly related to functional connectivity. This point will be discussed in some detail in Section 7.

3. Criticality in the brain

As we have seen, dynamical systems posed near the *critical point* are characterized by the emergence of collective, self-organized behavior. At the critical point the dimension of this collective mode is that of the whole system (giant cluster). This is associated with scale-free or

power-law behavior and long-range correlations. Although these properties, as we shall see, have been reported for brain dynamics, it is important to understand (i) whether criticality has been assessed for brain dynamics and, in case, (ii) which kind of criticality is taking place [14]. Given criticality for assessed, however, both in critical phenomena (i.e. second order phase transitions) [15] and in self-organized criticality [16,17] we expect similar behaviors. Indeed the system is either posed in, or moves towards, a critical value of a cooperation parameter driving the non-linear coupling among many individual units. This means that the system stays in, or reaches, a critical point, corresponding to a phase transition from an uncorrelated to a correlated condition. This hypothesis for brain dynamics is not new. In his pioneering work [18], Turing conjectured that an intelligent system cannot “live” either in a too much correlated condition (order, super-critical), or in a too chaotic one (disorder, sub-critical). More recently, theoretical studies have been performed, with similar conclusions (see, e.g., [19] or, more recently, [8,20,21]).

Many authors have investigated the spatial and/or structural complexity of neuronal network models, of *in vitro* and *in vivo* data and found features in agreement with criticality. These properties are (i) scale-free network topology in cross correlations and (ii) avalanches. Point (i) is advocated, e.g., by the authors of Refs. [8], who studied the functional connectivity of the brain defined through the network of above-threshold cross-correlations derived from fMRI data, which is again a structural property. They evaluated the degree distribution (the degree of a node is the number of links of that node with others), with different thresholds (normalized in terms of total number of links). What they found is that, experimentally, scale-free network structures stemming from cross-correlation functions of MRI voxels are indistinguishable from those stemming from a paradigmatic model for criticality, i.e., the Ising model for ferromagnetic materials, exactly at the Curie temperature.

As far as point (ii) is concerned, the presence of firing-neuron avalanches have been reported both *in vitro* and *in vivo* [22], and also at the level of EEG [23]. In particular, the authors of Refs. [22,24] found a scale-free distribution of avalanche (or cluster) sizes, which is a signature of spatial and structural long-range correlations, in network models and *in vitro* data.

4. Criticality, intermittency, seriality and consciousness

4.1. Criticality yields intermittency in global fluctuations

The above cited studies about criticality in the brain are focused on the spatial or structural complexity. Apart from a vast literature on scale-free dynamics and $1/f$ spectral properties, that have been reported starting from Novikov [25], an often overlooked property is the temporal complexity. We plan to shift the focus from *temporal* long-range correlations with power-law decay (equivalent to $1/f$ noise) to *time intermittency*, which is defined by the presence of *crucial events* in the complex/critical system. Intermittent events are defined as the time instants where

the system abruptly increases its entropy, due to short episodes of bursting activity, intermittently separated by quiescent *metastable* states. When the distribution density of the time durations of these metastable states are characterized by long tails (with infinite second moment) the events are called *crucial*, insofar as the overall entropy increase is sublinear, so the increase rate (Kolmogorov entropy) is null [26], a signature of complexity.

It was recently proved that the inverse-power-law decaying auto-correlation functions (equivalent, according to a generalized Wiener-Kintchine theorem [27,28] to $1/f$ noise) are typical of critical points of second-order phase transitions, and are ultimately due to **serial** intermittent dynamics driving the fluctuations of those macroscopic variables, called “order parameters”, averaging microscopic fluctuations. In particular, intermittency in critical systems was theoretically established in three dimensions, using a Landau treatment [29], and numerically [30] using a decision-making model, equivalent, at small couplings, to a 2D Ising Monte-Carlo. Remarkably, the results of [30] are robust with respect to changes in anatomical topology. In a nutshell, the macroscopic dynamics driving the fluctuations in system at the critical points are driven by intermittent events.

The authors of Refs. [30,29] found that the fluctuations of a random field at the critical point, i.e., the “order parameter” averaging microscopic fluctuations, are described in terms of a *Type-I intermittent* dynamical map similar to the well-known Manneville map [31], which describes turbulent bursting. Again, turbulent bursting is complex, as this kind of dynamical systems is characterized by the presence of a marginally unstable point determining an alternation between long time intervals with calm motion and short-time bursting events. These events, occurring in the temporal evolution of the order parameter, are crucial, since they are described by a serial fractal point process, i.e., a sequence of intermittent events that: (a) occur randomly in time and (b) display a slow (power-law) decay in the distribution of inter-event or Waiting Times (WTs).

Type-I intermittency is in agreement with a fast decay of memory in correspondence of event occurrences. In the language of stochastic processes, this is described by a *renewal point process* [32], which is defined by the condition of mutual statistical independence of the events and, consequently, of the WTs. In summary, the macroscopic fluctuations of a critical system are driven by a renewal point process, which is the mathematical tool used here to describe intermittency and, in the case of a self-similar of fractal distribution of WTs, *fractal intermittency*. The renewal condition is generated by burstiness with fast memory decay, and it was found to well describe the intermittency features of several complex systems, from blinking quantum dots [33,34] to turbulence [35–37] and brain dynamics [38]. The renewal property seems to play a crucial role in the perturbation of complex systems [39–43] and it is a fundamental assumption in the derivation of a new Fluctuation–Dissipation Theorem (FDT) based on renewal events [44,45], whose main prediction is that two complex systems have a maximum interaction when they have similar complexities. The power-law

relaxation foreseen by this new FDT was also experimentally validated in the weak turbulence regime of a liquid crystal [46].

4.2. The emergence of the global workspace

Basal EEG in healthy people have indeed been shown to produce $1/f$ noise through “events” associated with a global intermittent process of activation/deactivation of integrated networks [38].

From a psychophysiological point of view, the presence of a global serial intermittent process reconciles the apparent paradox of massive parallel computing units in the brain and the presence of a unique stream of consciousness, and corroborates the theory of a “global workspace” [47]. The concept of global workspace is the most widely accepted psychological and neurobiological way of describing consciousness [47,48]. It has been hypothesized that the existence of the workspace is made possible by reentrant loops in the neural topology [49], with the emergence of a global neural dynamic core, namely a serial mechanism coordinating a variety of integrated cores working in parallel.

Thus, a description of brain dynamics grounded on the physics of critical phenomena explains the long-range neural binding, like that well described by Chialvo [8], and provides, as earlier stated, the presence of a unique intermittent serial process that is essential in the description of consciousness. The emerging picture is a dynamical pattern of “thoughts” as a serial conscious output which integrates parallel non-conscious units. The serial, operational time [50] is characterized by the system visiting meta-stable states, with information only increasing at the transitions (quakes) between a metastable state and the next. All this can be operatively associated to segmentation in electroencephalogram (EEG) [51–53], namely to the fact that EEG signals frequently look like juxtapositions of epochs with stable frequency and amplitude, with abrupt changes, called rapid transition processes (RTP), from epoch to epoch.

In Fig. 1 we graphically summarize what we have reviewed thus far, namely how the hypothesis that awake resting-state brain activity can be successfully described in term of a system at a critical point.

5. Intermittency in brain dynamics

The existence of crucial events in the brain is well-established, as spontaneous neuronal activity exhibits relatively quiet periods in alternation with chaotic or bursty periods. Such brain events can be extracted from Electroencephalogram (EEG) data with detection algorithms. Events are here defined as abrupt transitions or Rapid Transition Processes (RTPs) [51–53]) to and from metastable states, via multichannel EEGs [38]. On short time scales brain events typically display a complex structure in terms of neuronal avalanches [23,55].

Exploiting the concept of RTP events, the temporal complexity of brain dynamics, in terms of intermittency features, has been investigated [38,23]. It was found that a

serial renewal process of global integration exists in the human brain during a *resting state* wake condition and that this renewal process has well-defined scaling exponents in both distributions of avalanche sizes and inter-event times [38,23]. These scaling exponents, being a signature of Type-I fractal intermittency, confirm the critical brain hypothesis [21]. The scaling exponents were evaluated through the diffusion scaling of different random walks driven by the RTP events (see details in the next Section 6). This approach based on diffusion scaling allowed to get a robust estimation of the intermittency exponent or *complexity index* μ , i.e., the exponent of the inverse power-law tail in the WT distribution: $\psi(\tau) \sim 1/\tau^\mu$. It is worth noting that similar approaches, based on brain events and point processes, have been recently applied, confirming the robust and universal critical behavior of brain dynamics and neuronal networks [55,56].

Is intermittency related to consciousness? All the above findings lead to the idea that consciousness is related with the emergence of criticality and fractal intermittency. However, this is just a hypothesis as it is not yet clear if this renewal fractal process is uniquely associated with consciousness or with a non-task-driven default mode activity [57], also present in non-conscious states like deep sleep.

In the following we clarify this point by evaluating the event-driven diffusion scaling of EEG data collected from the observation of healthy human subjects during sleep. The statistical analysis we use is essentially the same as in Ref. [38]. In Section 6 we describe the dataset and the methods of data analysis. In particular, we will introduce the diffusion scaling method. In Section 7 we show our results and we discuss the hypothesis that the emergence of intermittent events described by a (serial) renewal fractal process and of anomalous diffusion is a signature of consciousness, while the lack of fractal features and the emergence of normal diffusion could characterize non-conscious states.

6. Data description and methods of analysis

A normal night’s sleep consists of a few (from 4 to 6) cycles, each cycle consisting of different phases, defined on the presence of different “waves”, or graphoelements, and specific rhythms. After a pre-sleep wakefulness, the first cycle begins with a wake-sleep transition state called N1. As the sleep deepens, due to the diminished presence of various neurotransmitters, sleep phases N2 (shallow sleep) and N3 (deep, or Slow Wave Sleep, SWS) are visited one or more times, till the Rapid Eye Movement (REM) phase (typically a dreaming phase) occurs, that marks the end of the cycle. The phases N1, N2 and N3 (or SWS) are globally referred to as Non-REM (NREM) phase. At variance with NREM phase, REM is characterized by a high level of the acetylcholine (ACh) neurotransmitter. At the end of the first cycle, a second cycle begins, with or without N1 or wakefulness episodes (Wakefulness After Sleep Onset, WASO), with the presence of NREM sleep (AC regain drops to low values), again ending with a REM phases, and so on.

Data set. Our data set is composed of 29 whole-night high-density (128 channel, 4 ms sampling time) EEG recordings.

Fig. 1. Conceptual map of the literature analysis that represents the minimal background on which the present work is based. Dark boxes with white letters represent concepts, while arrowed gray boxes with black letters represent results well established in scientific literature of different fields (with different readerships). Examples of (a) are the works of Diakonou and Contoyiannis and of Turalaska et al. [29,30]; for (b) we make reference to the recent works of Chialvo, for instance [8]; (c) is a classic result of the theory of critical phenomena, see e.g., the book of Stanley [54]; there is a vast literature about result (d), see e.g., the work of Sporn [6,7]; for (e) see the reviews of Baars and Edelman et al. [47]; for (f) we refer to the recent review of Fingerkurts et al. [50]. Finally, literature (g) refers to the Tononi’s Integrated Information Theory [4,5].

Subjects slept two nights with the same experimental set-up, namely after an adaptation night the second one was recorded. All subjects signed informed consent according to local ethical committees. Through visual inspection of the polygraphic traces, namely a selection of few EEG channel plus miogram (muscle tone intensity) and oculogram (eye movements) all recordings were segmented into different cycles and phases. For the purpose of the present paper, however, we will focus on global properties of sleep in the various phases and we will freely make recourse to grand averages over the 29 whole-night recordings. Artifacts were semiautomatically removed, and only artifact-free segments of time duration longer than 3 min were kept for the RTP detection. We use only segments of the first cycle, as signal quality decreased in subsequent cycles.

Rapid transition processes. Herein, for each EEG channel, pass-band filtered between 0.3 and 40 Hz (Chebyshev II filter algorithm), RTPs are extracted as a “significant” selection of intersection between two different moving averages of the Hilbert transform of the signal modulus. Moving averages have windows of 20 and 500 ms, respectively. By significant we mean that we select only the points where the intersection between the two curves is above a threshold angle. To do this we select a 500 ms window surrounding the intersection and compute the sum of the modulus of the difference between the two curves. For each channel significant RTPs are those in the highest decile (the ones higher than 90% are chosen). Notice that the choice of RTPs described above is both different from that used by Kaplan [52] and from our group’s original recipe (see Fig. 1 of [23]). We however proved in [58] that our

subsequent analysis is robust with respect to a variation of event definition, and also in the presence of superimposed noise [59].

We are here interested on global events, i.e., on the “simultaneous” occurrences of RTP in different EEG channels. For each EEG recording, the sequence of coincidences, or (concurrent) Multi-Channel RTPs (MC-RTPs), is obtained from single-channel RTPs via the introduction of two thresholds: The first one, Δt_c , defines the maximum time distance for two single-channel RTPs (from different channels) to be considered concurrent; the second one, N_t , defines the minimum number of concurrent single-channel RTPs required for a MC-RTPs to be recorded as a global event. Since events that have a distance less than Δt_c are considered to be simultaneous, Δt_c must be small. We herein use $\Delta t_c = 4$ ms, equal to the instrumental sampling time, and $N_t = 5$. $N_t < 5$ suffered from first-neighbor effects, and $N_t > 5$ resulted behavior similar to that reported, but with decreased statistics.

Event-driven random walks and diffusion scaling. The random walks driven by renewal events [38,37] are inspired to the Continuous Time Random Walk (CTRW) of Montroll and co-workers [60,61]. In CTRW it is allowed to have random time steps, corresponding to a sequence of WTs from a renewal process. Here, the WT sequences derived from the EEG recordings are used to define two different CTRWs driven by the same RTP global events. Firstly, we introduce a discrete artificial signal $\zeta(t)$, i.e., a kind of random discontinuous velocity that changes value only in correspondence of event occurrences. In Figs. 2 and 3 a sketch of the two signals $\zeta(t)$ is reported. The times t_0, t_1, t_2, \dots correspond to the occurrence of the events $0, 1, 2, \dots$, while τ_1, τ_2, \dots

are the WTs, i.e., the time interval between the events 0 and 1, the events 1 and 2 and so on. In particular, we have:

- (a) Asymmetric Jump (AJ) rule: the walker makes a positive jump ($\xi(t_n) = 1$) in correspondence of each event n , otherwise it stands ($\xi(t) = 0$). Then, $\xi(t)$ is a sequence of pulses of constant intensity.
- (b) Symmetric Jump (SJ) rule: as in the AJ rule, but the walker can make positive or negative jumps in correspondence of an event: $\xi(t_n) = \pm 1$. The sign \pm is chosen with a coin tossing prescription.

Then, from the artificial signal $\xi(t)$ the diffusion variable of the CTRW is defined as follows:

$$X(t) = X_0 + \sum_{j=0}^{j=t} \xi(j) \Delta t, \quad (1)$$

being Δt the sampling time of the experimental time series.

The scaling properties of these random walks were extensively investigated in several papers (see [38,36,37] for a brief review) by applying the analytical methods of CTRW. Here we are interested in the scaling exponent H of the second moment

$$\sigma^2(t) = \langle (X(t) - \bar{X})^2 \rangle \sim t^{2H}, \quad (2)$$

where \bar{X} is the mean value of $X(t)$.

Analytical expressions of the scaling H as a function of the complexity index μ were determined in the case of renewal WTs with inverse power-law tail: $\psi(\tau) \sim 1/\tau^\mu$. These expressions $H = H(\mu)$ are reported in Fig. 4 and summarized in the following:

$$(AJ) \quad H_{AJ} = \begin{cases} \mu/2; & 1 < \mu < 2 \\ 2 - \mu/2; & 2 \leq \mu < 3 \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 3 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$(SJ) \quad H_{SJ} = \begin{cases} (\mu - 1)/2; & 1 < \mu < 2 \\ 1/2; & \mu \geq 2 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Both rules give a normal scaling $H = 1/2$ for $\mu \geq 3$, corresponding to normal (Gaussian) diffusion. For the SJ rule this is true also in the range $2 < \mu \leq 3$, while AJ rule is super-diffusive ($H > 1/2$) in all the interval $1 < \mu < 3$. On the contrary, the SJ rule is sub-diffusive ($H < 1/2$) for $1 < \mu < 2$. We note that, if the WTs comes from a Poisson process, the value of H is again $1/2$ and, in the long-time, we have a Gaussian diffusion.

Fig. 2. The SJ walking rules for the "velocity signal" $\xi(t)$.

Fig. 3. The AJ walking rules for the "velocity signal" $\xi(t)$.

Fig. 4. Diffusion scaling H vs. complexity index μ for SJ and AJ walking rules: AJ (continuous line), SJ (dotted-dashed line).

The joint use of these walking rules can be used to evaluate the value of the μ by inverting the expressions given in Eqs. (3) and (4). It can be seen from Fig. 4 that $H_{AJ}(\mu)$ is not an invertible function, as the same value of H corresponds to two distinct values of μ , one smaller and the other greater than 2. When $H_{SJ} < 1/2$ it results $\mu < 2$ and both rules, i.e., the associated values of μ derived from AJ and SJ rules, could be compared to each other. On the contrary, for $H_{SJ} = 1/2$, a value of μ cannot be derived from the SJ rule, but we can assume $\mu > 2$. For this reason, the SJ rule could be used to discriminate between $\mu < 2$ and $\mu > 2$, overcoming the ambiguity of AJ rule.

Detrended fluctuation analysis. The diffusion scaling H of the two random walks introduced above is estimated by means of Detrended Fluctuation Analysis (DFA) [62]. We briefly recall the main steps of this method:

- For a discrete time $L = 4, 5, \dots$, the time series of the diffusion process $X(t)$ is split into not-overlapping time windows of length L : $[kL + 1, kL + L]$. The window number is given by $[M/L]$, i.e., the integer part of M/L , being M the total length of the time series.
- For each time window $[kL + 1, kL + L]$ ($k = 0, 1, \dots, [M/L]$), the local trend is evaluated with a least-squares straight line fit: $\bar{X}_{k,L}(t) = a_{k,L}t + b_{k,L}$; $kL < t \leq (k+1)L$.
- The fluctuation is derived in the usual way: $\tilde{X}_{k,L}(t) = X(t) - \bar{X}_{k,L}(t) = X(t) - a_{k,L}t - b_{k,L}$; $kL < t \leq (k+1)L$.
- For a given time scale L , the mean-square deviation of the fluctuation is calculated over every window:

$$\begin{aligned} F^2(k, L) &= \frac{1}{L} \sum_{t=kL+1}^{(k+1)L} \tilde{X}_{k,L}^2(t) \\ &= \frac{1}{L} \sum_{t=kL+1}^{(k+1)L} (X(t) - \bar{X}_{k,L}(t))^2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

- Finally, an average over the windows is performed:

$$F^2(L) = \frac{1}{[M/L]} \sum_{k=0}^{[M/L]} F^2(k, L). \quad (6)$$

In the case of a self-similar process, it results: $F(L) \sim L^H$. Then, by defining, $z = \log(F(L))$ and $y = \log(L)$ it is possible to apply a least-squares straight line fit:

$$z = Hy + C, \quad (7)$$

where C is a constant.

Improvement of statistical accuracy in DFA. Given a time series of total length L , the DFA evaluation is reliable up to about $L/10$ and this is due to the lack of statistics in the long-time regime. However, we do not have only one time series, but several independent time segments, each one separated from the others by at least one artifact or phase shift in the original EEG recording. Several DFA curves can be obtained, one for each time segment, and then averaged to get a mean DFA curve. In this way, we are able to compute DFA up to a time given by the maximum among the values $L_i/10$, that is $\max_i(L_i/10)$, where i runs over all time segments and L_i is the total duration time of the i th time segment. Actually, the statistical accuracy remains stable up to a time given by $\min_i(L_i/10)$ and then decreases for longer time scales. In fact, the number of segments entering the average decreases very rapidly when approaching the time scale $\max_i(L_i/10)$. A common method to improve the statistics is *glueing* different segments together, in order to have a reliable DFA curve up to a time $(\sum_i L_i)/10$. This was done for instance for coding segments in DNA [62].

We improved the statistical accuracy on longer time scales, without the risk of making the running window explore spurious signal, i.e. that belong to different segments. Firstly, for each sleep phase, we evaluated the minimal duration time: $L_m = \min_i(L_i)$; then, for each segment, we computed the DFA up to time L_m ; finally, we performed the average over all the segments. Note that L_m is not only 10 times greater than $\min_i(L_i/10)$, but it is also greater than $\max_i(L_i/10)$. With this approach, a much better accuracy on long time scales is obtained. In fact, even if the statistical accuracy is low for the segments with the shortest duration times, the number of segments entering the average is greatly increased in the time range between $\min_i(L_i/10)$ and $L_m = \min_i(L_i)$, as all segments always enter in the average operation.

7. Results and discussion

Criticality has been found both in neuronal networks (models and *in vitro*, see Refs. [22,24]) and human brain [8] by investigating the spatial and structural complexity, while temporal complexity, i.e., time intermittency, in brain EEG was investigated in our previous papers (see Refs. [38,23]). In particular, from the analysis of EEG data in resting state (wakefulness) condition we found that the brain (RTP) events introduced by the authors of Refs.

[51,52] are driven by an underlying renewal fractal point process with well-defined scaling properties (**fractal intermittency**). As already said, it is not clear if fractal intermittency is uniquely associated with consciousness or with a non-task-driven default mode activity [57], also present in non-conscious states like deep (NREM) sleep. To clarify this point, let us summarize some observations about consciousness:

1. the conscious brain is associated with an emerging “giant cluster” or Global Workspace [47]) that co-exist with clusters of any size having scale-free size distribution, in analogy with what happens in critical systems (see e.g., [22,24] for dynamical avalanches, or [63] for oscillator synchronization);
2. conscious scenes are unitary and occur serially: only one scene at a time takes place [47];
3. consciousness is a sequence of metastable states (giant clusters), which reflect rapidly adaptive selection mechanisms in perception and memory; in the consciousness theory of Baars [47], the Global Workspace is an emerging serial process that, in some way, selects only one scene at a time from an underlying set of parallel scenes, and only this selected scene comes into consciousness;
4. In conscious states, there’s a competition among cooperative global integration and autonomous fragmentation; the interplay of these two components constitutes the metastable regime of brain dynamics and determines the complex intermittent behavior in the EEG field [50,64,5].
5. the renewal fractal process derived from EEG data, which is defined by the sequence of renewal RTP events, is a particular serial process, as only a global metastable state (giant cluster) at a time takes place and the short-time RTP events mark the death of a metastable state and the birth of a new one [38,23].

From the above observations, we are then lead to make the following assumption:

The renewal point process describing fractal intermittency, which is experimentally defined in EEG data by the sequence of global RTP events with inverse power-law distributed WTs, is a correlate of consciousness.

We validate this assumption by comparing different states of consciousness in healthy subjects during sleep. In Section 6 we have already given a description of the dataset and of the methods used to analyze the EEG data, which can be summarized as follows: (a) segmentation and artifact removal; (b) RTP detection, global brain events (c) computation of event-driven random walks (SJ and AJ) and estimation of second moment scaling H by applying DFA.

The diffusion scaling H of the SJ rule is definitively $H = 0.5$ for all time segments and subjects (data not shown for the sake of conciseness). This is a signature that the complexity index μ is greater than 2. In Fig. 5 we show the square root of the second moment $\sigma(t)$ for the AJ rule, averaged over all subjects and nights and over the time segments of sleep cycle I as explained at the end of Section 6.

The second moment scaling H switches from an anomalous diffusion scaling ($H = 0.75$) in the case of (pre-sleep) wake and REM phases to a normal diffusion scaling ($H = 0.5$) in deep (SWS) sleep. Inverting Eq. (3), this means that in wake and REM phases, which are conscious states, we get an average value $\mu = 2.5$, thus giving fractal intermittency and long-range correlations, whereas in the deep (SWS) sleep phase we get $\mu > 3$. We recall that normal diffusion ($H = 0.5$) is also in agreement with a Poisson condition, i.e., with exponentially distributed WTs or, more realistically, with an exponential cut-off emerging at relatively short WTs and, thus, with short-time correlations.

The normal diffusion regime during SWS phase could be explained in terms of the fragmentation of the Global Workspace into local, independent, functional units working in parallel, which is a condition known to be associated with the lack of consciousness. Notice that the fragmentation is related to the large number of Sleep Slow Oscillations (SSOs) during SWS [65,66], which determine a reset of the neuronal activity by means of a hyper-polarizing wave putting most neurons in a down-state, i.e., a state far from the activation threshold of the membrane potential. This is also called “electrical silence”. Finally, from a purely descriptive point of view, we can conclude that the result of Fig. 5 demonstrates that the scaling H , and the associated complexity index μ , could be proposed as a reliable indicator of conscious states. The interpretation of these results deserve further investigations that, however, will be the focus of future research work.

Surprisingly, the distribution of avalanche sizes does not change when comparing wakefulness, NREM and REM sleep. This means that, at variance with the intermittent behavior, the global topological features of the brain neuronal network are independent from the particular brain condition (wakefulness, REM, NREM). Fig. 6 illustrates the distribution $P(N)$ of avalanche sizes N , namely the number of electrodes simultaneously undergoing an RTP, within time tolerance $\Delta t = 4.0$ ms. The distribution,

Fig. 5. Asymptotic time range in the DFA computed for AJ rule applied to different sleep phases (cycle 1). Continuous and dashed lines are a guide to the eye for the slopes $H = 0.75$ and $H = 0.5$, respectively. In the inset we report the entire time range over which the DFA has been computed. Notice that, in the short-time range, the DFA of the three phases (WAKE, REM and SWS) are essentially superposed, all displaying normal diffusion.

confirming previous results [23], decays as $1/N^\nu$ with $\nu \lesssim 2$. No difference in the distribution is visible as a function of sleep phases.

Let us see heuristically how distribution $P(N)$ is related to the topology of functional connectivity. We recall that this property is classically derived from cross-correlation functions. Let us for simplicity omit the role of Δt , and consider concurrences as if the events in different electrodes were exactly at the same time. Since our signal is given by the dichotomous time series $\zeta(t)$ corresponding to the AJ rule, we only have a nonzero contribution for pairwise correlation functions only when we have a concurrence of events among electrodes. Defining C_2 as the sum of the integrals of all pairwise correlation functions

$$C_2 \equiv \sum_t \sum_{i < j} \zeta_t^{(i)} \zeta_t^{(j)}, \quad (8)$$

where $\zeta_t^{(i)}$ is the dichotomous signal stemming from channel i at time t , we can generalize this correlation measure for clusters of N electrodes as follows

$$C_N \equiv \sum_t \sum_{i < j < \dots < k} \zeta_t^{(i)} \zeta_t^{(j)} \dots \zeta_t^{(k)}, \quad (9)$$

where we consider all N -uples $\{i, j, \dots, k\}$ of electrodes, so that

$$P(N) = \frac{C_N}{\sum_N C_N}. \quad (10)$$

The result of $P(N)$ illustrated in Fig. 6 thus suggests that the wakefulness functional connectivity is preserved both during NREM and REM sleep. We can rigorously state that even in deep sleep spontaneous patterns emerge, with the same size distribution of those emerging during wakefulness or REM sleep.

Fig. 6. Probability density function $P(N)$ of the number of concurrent events for different stages, limited to the first sleep cycle. Concurrence is defined in the text, and holds within a tolerance time Δt , i.e. adopting the prescriptions of previous works [22,38,23]. Here $\Delta t = 4.0$ ms. WAKE refers to pre-sleep wakefulness. REM, N2 and SWS correspond to the different sleep stages as described in the section “Methods”. Dashed line is a guide to the eye corresponding to an inverse-power law with index $\nu = 1.9$.

8. Heuristic explanation based on physiology

In [67] it was shown how neural functional connectivity decreases in deep sleep, compared to wakefulness, after subliminal Trans-cranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS). It was therefore hypothesized that a pruned or simplified functional topology was responsible for the lack of consciousness, as it makes the system drifts away from the critical integration/segregation balance towards a more segregated state. Along this line, [71] recently reported that during NREM sleep the dynamics over different brain areas show an higher degree of independency (parallel computation) with respect to wakefulness and REM sleep. An even more recent paper confirms this behavior in anesthesia, i.e. during propofol-induced loss of consciousness [72]. Combining these important experimental results with the increasing evidence of criticality in brain functioning (at least during wakefulness) may lead to think that during NREM sleep the system drifts away from the critical regime. Does lack of consciousness mean that the system become supercritical or subcritical? The question, at the light of our results, is a little more complicated and further aspects have to be taken into proper consideration. The explanation we propose, illustrated in Fig. 7 aims at conciling the results presented herein and the known literature,

also taking into account that in biology a new form of criticality may take place, i.e. the *extended criticality* advocated by Bailly and Longo [73]. According to this view, some form of criticality always takes place in biological systems, that continuously drift from a critical point to another (for a review see [74]).

The onset of sleep is characterized by a reduction of neurotransmitters and hence of neural activity in the reticular ascending system, connecting the brain stem to the cortex. This is followed by a sensory deafferentation. Both mechanisms reduce the high frequency activity in the cell yielding a reduction in the amount of random activity onto synapses, or, in other words, of fluctuations. We expect therefore that the system becomes super-critical, i.e. more synchronized. On the other hand, the reduction in neurotransmitters may also decrease the effective coupling among neurons. As a result, it is also possible that the system stays globally critical, drifting from a critical condition to another. As a matter of fact, an indication of global criticality is given by the distribution $P(N)$ of quake sizes that remains unaltered throughout all sleep phases.

The stability of $P(N)$ with respect to sleep phases may be at odds with the results of [67]. It has to be said, however, that we are herein looking at spontaneous dynamics involving networks also composed of thalamic neurons,

Fig. 7. Schematic description of circular causation with and without consciousness. Left panel describes a classic scheme of circular causation in critical systems. Downwards arrows denote the dynamics of order parameters or, equivalently, the dynamic emergence of organized activity at a given level of description, which generates an organized structure at a larger-scale level. Upwards arrows denote the constraints imposed by the emergence of structures within a level to a smaller-scale level. The figure is inspired by Fig. 1 of [50], where the smallest scale level is the microscopic one, either associated to neural small structures or to *qualia* (the atoms of cognition); the second level is mesoscopic, associated to larger neural formations or to cognitive objects; the third is associated to a macroscopic neural level, or to phenomenal scenes. Here a further level is introduced, making it explicit the fact that, at criticality, activity clusters continuously form (events) and break, with only one giant cluster present at the time. Conversely, it also explicits the unitary nature of consciousness, and the emergence of a global workspace. In the right panel we see the modifications induced by the possibility of neural bistability, which is normally induced by large fluctuations: Till the level of phenomenal scenes the circular causation described by criticality is conserved; when a giant cluster is being formed the consequential large fluctuations directly reset the system at the microscopic neural level (long downwards arrow). As a consequence the global workspace never survives in its unitarity. This is graphically underlined by the use of a dashed line for the largest-scale.

rather than stimulated in a top-down fashion, hence shunting the thalamus, via TMS as in [67].

Sleeping brain is characterized by cellular bi-stability. Neurons during sleep are able, due to the opening of calcium-dependent potassium channels, to hyper-polarize down to negative potentials as low as -80 mV. This state, is normally referred to as “down state” or “electrical silence”. The reason of this behavior is under debate. Some explanations are given by different amounts of chemicals at the end of a prolonged wakefulness (*s*-process) [75]. For our purposes it is sufficient to recognize that after the onset of sleep certain neurons live in a thermodynamic state such that an afferent activity may locally generate the down state. When a coordinated pool of nearby neurons globally undergo the electrical silence, a giant EEG event takes place, called Sleep Slow Oscillation (SSO) [65,66] which is able to diffuse to a large portion of the scalp. SSO events mark the death of metastable states, and can be safely assumed to be renewal, since they reset the memory in vast areas of the scalp. Moreover, they are normally triggered by high levels of neural activity, normally detected as events by our procedure.

At the REM sleep onset, the abrupt and intense release of acetylcholine at the cortical level resets consciousness by blocking potassium channels [68] hence preventing neural bistability. On the other hand, the cholinergic activation of cortical and sub-cortical circuits yields a metabolic mapping typical of sensory/motor-emotional interaction. Indeed, emotional structures, such as amygdaloid complex, parahippocampal cortex, anterior cingulate, and sensory/motor structures such as primary motor cortex, somatosensory cortex, visual cortex, and auditory cortex are overactivated with respect to NREM sleep and, although non consistently reported, to wakefulness [69]. Finally, Massimini et al. [70] demonstrated that during REM sleep the cortical response to TMS stimulation spreads over the cortex as in wakefulness.

Putting everything together, we infer that after sleep onset, the main difference with the critical dynamics of wakefulness and REM stands at the highest level of dynamical integration among different areas (Fig. 7). At that level, in the waking brain the dynamics is globally integrated, namely a whole system dynamics exist that, via downwards causation, is in turn shared by all areas (left panel of Fig. 7). After the sleeping onset, a globally emerging large fluctuation actually puts different areas at rest, while, in between these resetting events, different areas undergo independent dynamics (right panel of Fig. 7). In other words, the very same (or a similar) functional connectivity that during wakefulness or REM, as a result of a large fluctuation (over a threshold), involves the global workspace, during SWS becomes a traveling Slow Sleep Oscillation that spreads through the cortex [66], and therefore resets the areas that initiated the fluctuation as well as other areas. This makes it impossible for the different areas to establish the long-range correlations observed in the genuinely critical states when consciousness takes place. In other words, the highest level of integration cannot correspond to a global workspace, and the brain activity is fragmented into parallel dynamics in between SSOs. These different mechanisms, however, make use of the same, or

similar, functional connectivity that is a remaining sign of the global critical dynamics happening during wakefulness. We remark that our focus on events makes it possible to study how the independence of neural activities in the different areas, already established in literature [71,72], is able to take place, exploiting, through the bistability wave called SSO, the very same connectivity that is able to maintain the sleep, but also to reinstate the critical conscious state of wakefulness.

We remark again that the scenario stemming from this work refers to the only physiological lack of consciousness, namely dreamless sleep. Further research and ad hoc experiments will be devoted to the study of pathological forms of unconsciousness, as it is not clear whether the route to unconsciousness due to sleep may be a good model for understanding these conditions. It is foreseeable that epileptic-related unconsciousness may share some mechanisms with sleep, while for other conditions like traumatic brain injuries (with wide-spread axonal injury) this similarity is expected to break down.

References

- [1] Nir Y, Tononi G. Dreaming and the brain: from phenomenology to neurophysiology. *Trends Cogn Sci* 2010;14:88–100.
- [2] Gell-Mann M. Consciousness, reduction, and emergence. *Ann New York Acad Sci* 2001;929:41–9; Feinberg TE. Neuroontology, neurobiological naturalism, and consciousness: a challenge to scientific reduction and a solution. *Phys Life Rev* 2011;9:13–34.
- [3] Werner G. From brain states to mental phenomena via phase space transitions and renormalization group transformation: proposal of a theory. *Cogn Neurodyn* 2012;6:199–202.
- [4] Balduzzi D, Tononi G. Integrated information in discrete dynamical systems: motivation and theoretical framework. *PLoS Comput Biol* 2008;4:e1000091.
- [5] Tononi G. Consciousness as integrated information: a provisional manifesto. *Biol Bull* 2008;215:216–42.
- [6] Bullmore E, Sporns O. Complex brain networks: graph theoretical analysis of structural and functional systems. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 2009;10:186–98; Bullmore E, Sporns O. The economy of brain network organization. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 2012;13:336–49.
- [7] Sporns O, Tononi G, Edelman GM. Theoretical neuroanatomy: relating anatomical and functional connectivity in graphs and cortical connection matrices. *Cereb Cortex* 2000;10:127141 [for a popular review see]; Zimmer C. 100 Trillion connections. *Sci Am* 2011;304:58–63 [and references therein].
- [8] Chialvo DR. Emergent complex neural dynamics. *Nat Phys* 2010;6:744–50; Fraiman D, Balenzuela P, Foss J, Chialvo DR. Ising-like dynamics in large-scale functional brain networks. *Phys Rev E* 2009;79:061922.
- [9] Kitzbichler MG, Smith ML, Christensen SR, Bullmore E. Broadband criticality of human brain network synchronization. *PLoS Comput Biol* 2009;5:e1000314.
- [10] Hollingshad NW, Turalska M, Allegrini P, West BJ, Grigolini P. A new measure of network efficiency. *Physica A* 2012;391:1894–9.
- [11] Turalska M, Geneston E, West BJ, Allegrini P, Grigolini P. *Front Physiol* 2012;3:52:1–7.
- [12] De Arcangelis L, Perrone-Capano C, Herrmann HJ. Self-organized criticality model for brain plasticity. *Phys Rev Lett* 2006;96:028107:1–7:4.
- [13] Zapperi S, Baekgaard LK, Stanley HE. Self-organized branching processes: mean-field theory for avalanches. *Phys Rev Lett* 1995;75:4071–4.
- [14] Lovecchio E, Allegrini P, Geneston E, West BJ, Grigolini P. From self-organized to extended criticality. *Front Physiol* 2012;3:98. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2012.00098>.
- [15] Sornette D. *Critical phenomena in natural sciences*. Berlin: Springer-Verlag; 2006.

- [16] Jensen HJ. Self-organized criticality. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1998.
- [17] Bak P, Tang C, Wiesenfeld K. Self-organized criticality: an explanation of the $1/f$ noise. *Phys Rev Lett* 1987;59:381; Bak P, Tang C, Wiesenfeld K. Self-organized criticality. *Phys Rev A* 1988;38:364.
- [18] Turing AM. Computing machinery and intelligence. *Mind* 1950;59:433–60.
- [19] Chialvo DR, Bak P. Learning from mistakes. *Neuroscience* 1999;90:1137–48.
- [20] Werner G. Viewing brain processes as critical state transitions across level of organization: neural events in cognition and consciousness, and general principles. *Biosystems* 2009;96:114–9.
- [21] Tagliazucchi E, Chialvo DR. The collective brain is critical, arXiv:1103.2070v1[q-bio.NC], 2011.
- [22] Beggs JM, Plenz D. Neuronal avalanches in neocortical circuits. *J Neurosci* 2003;23:11167–77; Plenz D, Thiagarjan TC. The organizing principles of neuronal avalanches: cell assemblies in the cortex? *Trends Neurosci* 2007;30:101–10.
- [23] Allegrini P, Paradisi P, Menicucci D, Gemignani A. Fractal complexity in spontaneous EEG metastable state transitions: new vistas on integrated neural activity. *Front Physio* 2010;1:128.
- [24] Pellegrini GL, de Arcangelis L, Hermann HJ, Perrone-Capano C. Activity-dependent neural network model on scale-free networks. *Phys Rev E* 2007;76:016107.
- [25] Novikov E, Novikov A, Shannahoff-Khalsa D, Schwartz B, Wright J. Scale-similar activity in the brain. *Phys Rev E* 1997;56:R2387–9.
- [26] Grigolini P, Pala MG, Palatella L, Roncaglia R. Towards the thermodynamics of localization processes. *Phys Rev E* 2000;62:34293436.
- [27] Lukovic M, Grigolini P. Power spectra for both interrupted and perennial aging processes. *J Chem Phys* 2008;129:184102.
- [28] Lowen SB, Teich MC. Fractal renewal processes generate $1/f$ noise. *Phys Rev E* 1993;47:992–1001.
- [29] Contoyiannis YF, Diakonou FK. Criticality and intermittency in the order parameter space. *Phys Lett A* 2000;268:286; Contoyiannis YF, Diakonou FK, Malakis A. On the intermittent dynamics of critical fluctuations. *Phys Rev Lett* 2002;89:035701.
- [30] Turala M, West BJ, Grigolini P. Temporal complexity of the order parameter at the phase transition. *Phys Rev E* 2011;83:061142.
- [31] Manneville P. Intermittency, self-similarity and $1/f$ Spectrum in dissipative dynamical systems. *Journal de Physique (France)* 1980;41:1235–43.
- [32] Cox DR. *Renewal theory*. London: Methuen & Co. Ltd.; 1962.
- [33] Paradisi P, Allegrini P, Barbi F, Bianco S, Grigolini P. Renewal, modulation and blinking quantum dots. *AIP Conf Proc* 2005;800:92–7.
- [34] Bianco S, Grigolini P, Paradisi P. Fluorescence intermittency in blinking quantum dots: renewal of modulation? *J Chem Phys* 2005;123:174704.
- [35] Paradisi P, Cesari R, Contini D, Donateo A, Palatella L. Characterizing memory in atmospheric time series: an alternative approach based on renewal theory. *Eur Phys J Special Topics* 2009;174:207–18.
- [36] Paradisi P, Cesari R, Donateo A, Contini D, Allegrini P. Scaling laws of diffusion and time intermittency generated by coherent structures in atmospheric turbulence. *Nonlinear Proc Geoph* 2012;19:113–26.
- [37] Paradisi P, Cesari R, Donateo A, Contini D, Allegrini P. Diffusion scaling in event-driven random walks: an application to turbulence. *Rep Math Phys* 2012;70:205–20.
- [38] Allegrini P, Menicucci D, Bedini R, Fronzoni L, Gemignani A, Grigolini P, et al. Spontaneous brain activity as a source of ideal $1/f$ noise. *Phys Rev E* 2009;80:061914:1–061914:13.
- [39] Akin OC, Paradisi P, Grigolini P. Periodic trend and fluctuations: the case of strong correlation. *Physica A* 2006;371:157–70.
- [40] Allegrini P, Barbi F, Grigolini P, Paradisi P. Aging and renewal events in sporadically modulated systems. *Chaos, Solitons Fract* 2007;34:11–8.
- [41] Bianco S, Grigolini P, Paradisi P. A fluctuating environment as a source of periodic modulation. *Chem Phys Lett* 2007;438(4–6):336–40.
- [42] Paradisi P, Cesari R, Grigolini P. Superstatistics and renewal critical events. *Cent Eur J Phys* 2009;7:421–31.
- [43] Akin OC, Paradisi P, Grigolini P. Perturbation-induced emergence of Poisson-like behavior in non-Poisson systems. *J Stat Mech: Theory Exp* 2009:P01013. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1088/1742-5468/2009/01/P01013>.
- [44] Allegrini P, Bologna M, Grigolini P, West BJ. Fluctuation-dissipation theorem for event-dominated processes. *Phys Rev Lett* 2007;99:010603; Aquino G, Bologna M, Grigolini P, West BJ. Beyond the death of linear response: $1/f$ optimal information transport. *Phys Rev Lett* 2010;105:040601:1–1:4; Aquino G, Bologna M, West BJ, Grigolini P. Transmission of information between complex systems: $1/f$ resonance. *Phys Rev E* 2011;83:051130:1–051130:12.
- [45] Allegrini P, Paradisi P, Menicucci D, Bedini R, Gemignani A, Fronzoni L. Noisy cooperative intermittent processes: from blinking quantum dots to human consciousness. *J Phys: Conf Ser* 2011;306:012027.
- [46] Silvestri L, Fronzoni L, Grigolini P, Allegrini P. Event-driven power-law relaxation in weak turbulence. *Phys Rev Lett* 2009;102:014502; Allegrini P, Bologna M, Fronzoni L, Grigolini P, Silvestri L. Experimental quenching of harmonic stimuli: universality of linear response theory. *Phys Rev Lett* 2009;103:030602.
- [47] Baars BJ. *A cognitive theory of consciousness*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 1998; Edelman GM, Gally JA, Baars BJ. *Biology of consciousness*. *Front Psychol* 2011;2:4.
- [48] Franklin S, Graesser A. A software agent model of consciousness. *Conscious Cogn* 1999;8:285301.
- [49] Edelman GM. *Neural darwinism: the theory of neuronal group selection*. New York: Basic Books; 1987; Edelman GM. *The remembered present*. New York: Basic Books; 1989; Edelman GM. *Naturalizing consciousness: a theoretical framework*. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2003;100:5520–4; Edelman GM, Tononi G. *A universe of consciousness: how matter becomes imagination*. New York: Basic Books; 2000.
- [50] Fingelkurts AA, Fingelkurts AA, Neves CFH. Natural world physical, brain operational, and mind phenomenal spacetime. *Phys Life Rev* 2010;7:195249.
- [51] Fingelkurts AA, Fingelkurts AA. Operational architectonics of the human brain biopotential field: towards solving the mind–brain problem. *Brain and Mind* 2001;2:261–96.
- [52] Kaplan AY, Fingelkurts AA, Fingelkurts AA, Borisov BS, Darkhovskiy BS. Nonstationary nature of the brain activity as revealed by EEG/EMG: methodological, practical and conceptual challenges. *Signal Process* 2005;85:2190–212.
- [53] Fingelkurts AA, Fingelkurts AA. Brain–mind operational architectonics imaging: technical and methodological aspects. *Open Neuroimag J* 2008;2:73–93.
- [54] Stanley HE. *Introduction to phase transitions and critical phenomena*. London: Oxford University Press; 1971.
- [55] Lombardi F, Herrmann HJ, Perrone-Capano C, Plenz D, de Arcangelis L. Balance between excitation and inhibition controls the temporal organization of neuronal avalanches. *Phys Rev Lett* 2012;108:228703.
- [56] Tagliazucchi E, Balenzuela P, Fraiman D, Chialvo DR. Criticality in large-scale brain fMRI dynamics unveiled by a novel point process analysis. *Front Physio* 2012;3:15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2012.00015>.
- [57] Raichle ME, MacLeod AM, Snyder AZ, Powers WJ, Gusnard DA, Shulman GL. A default mode of brain function. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2001;98:676–82.
- [58] Allegrini P, Menicucci D, Bedini R, Gemignani A, Paradisi P. Complex intermittency blurred by noise: theory and application to neural dynamics. *Phys Rev E* 2010;82:015103.
- [59] Allegrini P, Grigolini P, West BJ. A dynamical approach to DNA sequences. *Phys Lett A* 1996;211:217.
- [60] Montroll EW. Random walks on lattices. *Proc. Symp. Appl. Math.*, vol. 16. Am. Math. Soc.; 1964. p. 193–220.
- [61] Weiss GH, Rubin RJ. Random walks: theory and selected applications. *Adv Chem Phys* 1983;52:363–505.
- [62] Peng C-K, Buldyrev SV, Havlin S, Simons M, Stanley HE, Goldberger AL. Mosaic organization of DNA nucleotides. *Phys Rev E* 1994;49:1685.
- [63] Strogatz SH. From Kuramoto to Crawford: exploring the onset of synchronization in populations of coupled oscillators. *Phys D: Nonlinear Phenom* 2000;143:1–20.
- [64] Tononi G, Edelman GM. Consciousness and complexity. *Science* 1998;282:1846–51.
- [65] Massimini M, Huber R, Ferrarelli F, Hill S, Tononi G. The sleep slow oscillation as a traveling wave. *J Neurosci* 2004;24:6862–70; Piarulli A, Menicucci D, Gemignani A, Olcese U, d’Ascanio P, Pingitore A, et al. Likeness-based detection of sleep slow oscillations in normal and altered sleep conditions: application on low-density EEG recordings. *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng* 2009;57:363–72; Menicucci D, Piarulli A, Debarnot U, d’Ascanio P, Landi A, Gemignani

- A. Functional structure of spontaneous sleep slow oscillation activity in humans. *PLoS one* 2009;4:e7601.
- [66] Menicucci D, Piarulli A, Allegrini P, Laurino M, Mastorci F, Sebastiani L, Bedini R, Gemignani A. Fragments of wake-like activity frame down-states of sleep slow oscillations in humans: new vistas for studying homeostatic processes during sleep. *Int J Psychophysiol* 2013. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpsycho.2013.01.014>.
- [67] Massimini M, Ferrarelli F, Huber R, Esser SK, Singh H, Tononi G. Breakdown of cortical effective connectivity during sleep. *Science* 2005;309(5744):2228–32.
- [68] Rudolph M, Pelletier JG, Paré D, Destexhe A. Characterization of synaptic conductances and integrative properties during electrically induced EEG-activated states in neocortical neurons in vivo. *J Neurophysiol* 2005;94:2805–21.
- [69] Hobson JA. REM sleep and dreming: towards a theory of protoconsciousness. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 2009;10:803–13; Hobson JA, Pace-Schott EF. The cognitive neuroscience of sleep: neuronal systems, consciousness and learning. *Nat Rev Neurosci* 2002;3:679–93.
- [70] Massimini M, Ferrarelli F, Murphy M, Huber R, Riedner B, Casarotto S, et al. Cortical reactivity and effective connectivity during REM sleep in humans. *Cogn Neurosci* 2010;1:176–83.
- [71] Boly M, Perlberg V, Marrelec G, Schabus M, Laureys S, Doyon J, et al. Hierarchical clustering of brain activity during human nonrapid eye movement sleep. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2012;109:5856–61.
- [72] Lewis LD, Weiner VS, Mukamel EA, Donoghue JA, Eskandar EN, Madsen JR, et al. Rapid fragmentation of neuronal networks at the onset of propofol-induced unconsciousness. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 2012;109:E3377–86.
- [73] Bailly F, Longo G. *Mathematics and the Natural Sciences. The physical singularity of Life*. Singapore: College Press/World Scientific; 2011 [preliminary version, in French: Hermann, Paris, 2006].
- [74] Longo G, Montévil M. The inert vs. the living state of matter: extended criticality, time geometry, anti-entropy – an overview. *Front Physiol* 2012;3:39:1–8.
- [75] Borbély AA. A two process model of sleep regulation. *Human Neurobiol* 1982;1:195–204.